

ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS. PART VI.
2-HYDROXY-3-NAPHTHOIC ACIDS IN THE DETERMINATION
OF THORIUM AND ZIRCONIUM

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2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its acetyl, bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso derivatives have been used for the gravimetric determination of thorium and zirconium. Separation of thorium from the cerite earths and of thorium and zirconium from a number of foreign ions have been carried out with the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso compounds. They may also be used for the extraction of thorium from monazite sands. A considerable amount of zirconium may be separated from a smaller quantity of thorium when present in a mixture. Separation of thorium from uranium with the bromo, iodo and nitro compounds have also been described.

In Part V of this series (Datta, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 238), the possibility of using 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its various derivatives as analytical reagents for various cations has been discussed and the methods for the gravimetric estimation of cobalt with 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid have been described. This latter acid has also been successfully employed in the determination of palladium and uranium (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 155, 16). In the present communication the comparative utility of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso derivatives in the determination of thorium and zirconium has been investigated. Among all the acids used, the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso compounds have been proved suitable. Separation of thorium and zirconium from various foreign ions has also been made possible.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (B.D.H. reagent grade) was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol. 4:6-Dinitro-, 1-bromo-, 1:6-di-iodo-, 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acids and 2-acetyl-3-naphthoic acid were prepared and purified according to the methods described previously (Datta, *loc. cit.*). 1% Solutions of nitro and nitroso compounds were prepared in hot water. An 1% solution of nitroso compound was also prepared in acetic acid by dissolving 1 g. of the substance in 30 c.c. of glacial acetic acid with the aid of heat and then diluting it to 100 c.c. with water. 1% Solutions of the other reagents were prepared in alcohol (75%).

Stock solutions of thorium and zirconium nitrates (A.R., Merck) were prepared and estimated with 2:4-D (Datta and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 397) and benzoic acid (Venkatramaniah and Rao, *ibid.*, 1951, 28, 257; Klungenberg and Mendel, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 734) respectively. Stock solutions of other metals (all reagent grades) were prepared from their nitrates or chlorides and the metal contents determined by standard methods.

Optimum Conditions for the Determination of Thorium and Zirconium

Influence of p_H .—In order to find out a suitable p_H range for the estimation of thorium and zirconium with these reagents, precipitations were carried out in boiling solutions having different acid concentrations. A quantity of ammonium acetate was added in most of the cases. p_H of the solutions was measured after each precipitation. The results have been expressed as ThO_2 and ZrO_2 , obtained after ignition of the precipitate, in Table I and Table II respectively. It appears from these tables that zirconium is precipitated from solutions at a lower p_H than thorium with the same reagent.

TABLE I

Precipitation of thorium at different p_H .

ThO_2 taken = 0.0216 g.

(-N indicates-3-naphthoic acid)

No. of reagent.	Reagent.	Th O ₂ (in g.) found at p_H				
		2.6.	3.3.	3.8.	4.3.	5.3.
R ₁	2-OH-N	0.0101	0.0132	0.0193	0.0212	0.0213
R ₂	1-Br-2-OH-N	0.0123	0.0156	0.0216	0.0217	0.0214
R ₃	1 : 6-Di-I-OH-N	0.0128	0.0201	0.0214	0.0213	0.0212
R ₄	2-Acetyl-N	0.0072	0.0150	0.0173	0.0217	0.0214
R ₅	4 : 6-Di-NO ₂ -2OH-N	0.0130	0.0209	0.0212	0.0216	0.0217
R ₆	1-NO-2 OH-N	0.0110	0.0131	0.0215	0.0214	0.0212

TABLE II

Precipitation of zirconium at different p_H .

ZrO_2 taken = 0.0360 g.

Reagent.	Z r O ₂ (in g.) found at p_H				
	2.0.	3.1.	3.6.	4.1.	5.2.
R ₁	0.0173	0.0293	0.0355	0.0357	0.0353
R ₂	0.0191	0.0301	0.0354	0.0357	0.0357
R ₃	0.0187	0.0354	0.0356	0.0359	0.0358
R ₄	0.0105	0.0283	0.0356	0.0356	0.0350
R ₅	0.0296	0.0354	0.0363	0.0361	0.0359
R ₆	0.0355	0.0358	0.0364	0.0362	0.0357

Effect of Temperature.—These acids do not produce complete precipitation in the cold. The precipitate becomes colloidal on long boiling. Hence, precipitation should be carried out from solutions at a temperature, little below the boiling point. Best results were obtained at 80°.

Effect of Ammonium Acetate.—A small amount of ammonium acetate is necessary for the complete precipitation of thorium and zirconium with all the reagents excepting the nitro and the nitroso derivatives. An excess of ammonium acetate, however, inhibits complete precipitation.

The thorium or zirconium solution was neutralised to Congo red, 25 c.c. of the reagent solution added and the mixture heated to 80° with the subsequent addition of a definite quantity of a 2% solution of ammonium acetate. The effect of ammonium acetate in the precipitation of metals has been indicated in Table III.

TABLE III

ThO₂ taken = 0.0432 g. ZrO₂ taken = 0.0360 g. Total vol. = 50 c.c.

Reagent.	Am. acetate (2%) added (in c.c.).	ThO ₂ found (in g.).	ZrO ₂ found (in g.).
R ₁	0.5; 1.5; 2.0	0.0418; 0.0426; 0.0424	0.0332; 0.0353; 0.0340
R ₂	0.5; 1.2; 1.5	0.0426; 0.0428; 0.0424	0.0357; 0.0354; 0.0350
R ₃	0.5; 0.8; 1.0	0.0434; 0.0429; 0.0428	0.0358; 0.0360; 0.0354
R ₄	0.5; 1.0; 1.5	0.0420; 0.0426; 0.0430	0.0352; 0.0355; 0.0355
R ₅	—; 0.5; 1.0	0.0430; 0.0432; 0.0426	0.0360; 0.0361; 0.0355
R ₆	—; 0.5; 1.5	0.0434; 0.0433; 0.0425	0.0361; 0.0360; 0.0344

Analytical Procedure.—An aliquot quantity of thorium or zirconium solution, made neutral to Congo red, was heated to 80°. To this was added with stirring an 1% solution of the reagent, followed by 1 c.c. of a 2% ammonium acetate solution. In the case of nitro and nitroso compounds, an 1% solution in hot water was used, while other reagents were used in solutions of alcohol (75%). The mixture was further heated for 5 minutes on a boiling water-bath so that the precipitate became coarser and collected at the bottom of the beaker. 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its bromo and iodo compounds furnished yellow precipitates of thorium and zirconium; with acetyl compound the colour of the precipitates was white, while the nitro and nitroso compounds formed deep yellow precipitates. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and then with alcohol. After drying at 110°, the precipitate was ignited to the oxide to a constant weight. Some of the representative results have been tabulated below. Of the six reagents used, only the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso derivatives are suitable for the determination of these metals, and up to 4 mg. of these metals may be estimated with nearest accuracy.

TABLE IV

Determination of thorium and zirconium.

ThO ₂ taken.	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	R ₃ .	R ₄ .	R ₅ .	R ₆ .
	T h O ₂ f o u n d.					
0.0432 g.	0.0427 g.	0.0428 g.	0.0433 g.	0.0429 g.	0.0433 g.	0.0435 g.
0.0216	0.0212	0.0214	0.0218	0.0212	0.0217	0.0218
0.0162	0.0157	0.0159	0.0162	0.0156	0.0161	0.0162
0.0041	0.0030	0.0038	0.0040	0.0033	0.0040	0.0041
ZrO ₂ taken.	Z r O ₂ f o u n d.					
0.0405 g.	0.0399	0.0413	0.0403	0.0398	0.0408	0.0407
0.0270	0.0256	0.0269	0.0272	0.0264	0.0271	0.0274
0.0180	0.0174	0.0180	0.0181	0.0176	0.0182	0.0183
0.0045	0.0036	0.0040	0.0041	0.0036	0.0042	0.0044

*Attempted Separation of Thorium and Zirconium with
1-Nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid*

Zirconium is precipitated at a lower p_H than thorium with 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid. It was observed from preliminary experiments that zirconium could be precipitated in presence of considerable quantities of acetic acid, and not the latter. Attempts were therefore made to separate thorium from zirconium in acetic acid solution.

The solution containing the two metals was nearly evaporated to dryness; to the residue was added a considerable amount of 3.5*N* acetic acid solution, diluted to about 40 c.c. with water, and precipitation was carried out as before with the reagent. The washed precipitate was dissolved in the minimum quantity of dilute nitric acid with the aid of heat; requisite amount of acetic acid was then added and precipitation repeated. The precipitate was washed, dried and ignited to ZrO_2 as usual. The combined filtrate was evaporated to a small volume; thorium was precipitated from it as hydroxide with ammonia and ignited to oxide. The presence of thorium, if any, in the zirconium precipitate was tested with 'SNANDS' reagents (Datta, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 149, 270). The results recorded in Table V indicate that only a small amount of thorium, if present, can be removed from zirconium.

TABLE V

Separation of thorium from zirconium with 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid.

Metals taken.		3.5 <i>N</i> -acetic acid added.	Metals found.	
ZrO ₂ .	ThO ₂ .		ZrO ₂ .	ThO ₂ .
0.0270 g.	0.0162 g.	5 c.c.	0.0351 g.	...
0.0270	0.0162	10	0.0310	...
0.0270	0.0162	15	0.0293	0.0132 g.
0.0270	0.0162	20	0.0275	0.0158
0.0270	0.0162	25	0.0272	0.0160
0.0270	0.0216	30	0.0296	0.0193
0.0270	0.0216	40	0.0287	0.0198

Separation of Thorium from Rare-earth.

Separation of thorium from the cerite earths was carried out with the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso derivatives only; the other two were found unsuitable. The mixture was neutral to Congo red and thorium was precipitated and estimated as before. The results shown in Table VI reveal that bromo and iodo compounds may separate thorium from a mixture having thoria-earth oxide ratio = 1:15, the corresponding ratio for the nitro and nitroso compounds is 1:18. The slight contamination may easily be removed by double precipitation.

TABLE VI

ThO₂ taken = 0.0122 g.

CeO ₂ added.	La ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ : RO.		ThO ₂ found.	CeO ₂ added.	La ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ : RO.		ThO ₂ found.
		By R ₁ .	R ₂ .				By R ₃ .	R ₄ .	
0.0276 g.	...	1 : 2.3		0.0126 g.	0.1104 g.	0.0304 g.	1 : 11.5		0.0124 g.
0.0552	0.0304 g.	1 : 7		0.0127	0.1104	0.0912	1 : 16		0.0127
0.1104	0.0912	1 : 16		0.0129	0.1104	0.0988	1 : 17		0.0130
		By R ₅ .					By R ₆ .		
0.0552	0.0304	1 : 7		0.0123	0.1104	0.0380	1 : 12		0.0125
0.1104	0.0380	1 : 12		0.0125	0.1104	0.0912	1 : 16		0.0126
0.1104	0.1140	1 : 18		0.0127	0.1104	0.1140	1 : 18		0.0128

Separation of Thorium and Zirconium from Diverse Ions

Definite quantities of metal salt solutions were separately added to a fixed amount of thorium or zirconium solution. The p_n of the mixture containing thorium was brought to 3.8 and that containing zirconium to 3.5, by adding buffer solutions. The precipitations of thorium and zirconium were carried out as before with the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso compounds. It was found that these metals could be separated from a number of foreign ions, Cu, Cd, Bi, Ca, Ba, Sr, Zn, Mg, Cr, Mn, Ni and V. Pb^{II}, Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, and Ce^{IV} interfere in the determination with all these reagents. Aluminium and titanium cause heavy interference with the nitro compound, while cobalt, palladium and uranium (Datta, *loc. cit.*) exhibit quantitative interference with the nitroso compound. The results have been indicated in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Metal oxide added.	ThO ₂ taken = 0.0216 g.				ZrO ₂ taken = 0.0180 g.				
	Th O ₂ f o u n d b y				Z r O ₂ f o u n d b y				
	R ₂ .	R ₃ .	R ₅ .	R ₆ .	R ₁ .	R ₃ .	R ₅ .	R ₆ .	
CuO	0.0203 g.	0.0213 g.	0.0215 g.	0.0213 g.	0.0218 g.	0.0181 g.	0.0177 g.	0.0184 g.	0.0182 g.
CdO	0.0317	0.0212	0.0214	0.0218	0.0215	0.0182	0.0183	0.0180	0.0182
BiO	0.0281	0.0214	0.0217	0.0218	0.0216	0.0178	0.0182	0.0184	0.0183
CaO	0.0132	0.0213	0.0213	0.0215	0.0214	0.0180	0.0181	0.0179	0.0184
BaO	0.0250	0.0212	0.0215	0.0217	0.0216	0.0177	0.0178	0.0183	0.0181
SrO	0.0218	0.0215	0.0213	0.0218	0.0216	0.0182	0.0180	0.0184	0.0184
ZnO	0.0153	0.0213	0.0214	0.0213	0.0212	0.0181	0.0176	0.0180	0.0183
*Cr ₂ O ₃	0.0232	0.0212	0.0214	0.0217	0.0219	0.0184	0.0183	0.0183	0.0182
MnO ₂	0.0105	0.0212	0.0215	0.0214	0.0218	0.0176	0.0183	0.0179	0.0181
MgO	0.0139	0.0214	0.0216	0.0216	0.0218	0.0179	0.0184	0.0182	0.0183
V ₂ O ₅	0.0131	0.0212	0.0213	0.0212	0.0213	0.0175	0.0177	0.0177	0.0183
*NiO	0.0266	0.0218	0.0217	0.0217	0.0216	0.0184	0.0184	0.0183	0.0184
*CoO	0.0167	0.0213	0.0214	0.0217	...	0.0182	0.0184	0.0184	...
PdO	0.0216	0.0211	0.0213	0.0218	...	0.0181	0.0183	0.0180	...
*Al ₂ O ₃	0.0232	0.0212	0.0211	0.0213	0.0213	0.0185	0.0181	0.0184	0.0183
TiO ₂	0.0252	0.0213	0.0212	...	0.0220	0.0178	0.0184	...	0.0185

Separation of Thorium from Uranium

The bromo, iodo and nitro derivatives of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid may also be used for the separation of thorium from a large amount of uranium. Thorium was therefore precipitated with the three reagents from mixtures containing different quantities of thorium and uranium by following the same procedure. It was observed that the bromo, iodo and nitro compounds may separate thorium from mixtures having thoria-uranium oxide ratio up to 1 : 17, 1 : 18 and 1 : 21 respectively by double precipitation method. The results are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

ThO ₂ taken.	U ₃ O ₈ added.	ThO ₂ : U ₃ O ₈ .	Th O ₂ found by		
			R ₂ .	R ₃ .	R ₅ .
0.0122 g.	0.0424 g.	1 : 3.5	0.0125 g.	0.0123 g.	0.0123 g.
0.0122	0.1060	1 : 8.7	0.0126	0.0123	0.0124
0.0122	0.1696	1 : 13.5	0.0126	0.0125	0.0124
0.0122	0.2120	1 : 17.3	0.0127	0.0126	0.0125
0.0162	0.3074	1 : 18.3	0.0170	0.0167	0.0166
0.0162	0.3498	1 : 21.5	...	0.0170	0.0167
0.0162	0.3710	1 : 22.9	...	0.0174	0.0169

Extraction of Thorium from Monazite Sand

The four reagents, viz., the bromo, iodo, nitro and nitroso compounds of 2-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, were used for the extraction of thorium from monazite sand. The precipitation was carried out as before from the acid extract of the sands; the precipitate was washed several times with hot water in order to remove the adhering cerite earths completely and ignited to the oxide. Estimation with 2:4-D (Datta and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) was also carried out side by side for comparison. The results are recorded in Table IX.

TABLE IX

Reagent.	Wt. of sample.	Wt. of ThO ₂ obtd.	% Recovery of ThO ₂ .
R ₂	1.3250 g.	0.0966 g.	7.29
	1.1232	0.0820	7.30
R ₃	1.5031	0.1089	7.30
	1.3250	0.0968	7.31
R ₅	1.3250	0.0970	7.32
	1.1232	0.0821	7.31
R ₆	1.3250	0.0967	7.30
	1.1232	0.0822	7.32
2 : 4-D	1.1232	0.0821	7.31
	1.5031	0.1100	7.32

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